

МЕДИЦИНА, ПЕДАГОГИКА И ТЕХНОЛОГИЯ: ТЕОРИЯ И ПРАКТИКА

Researchbib Impact factor: 11.79/2023

SJIF 2024 = 5.444

Том 2, Выпуск 9, 30 Сентябрь

INFORMATION PROTECTION AND ITS TYPES

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Abstract: This article provides an analysis of information, information security, secret information, documented information, confidential information, principles of information security, and the main elements of information security .

Key words: Basic phrases: information, information security, public information, confidential information, documented information, confidential information.

Enter

Information security - from random and targeted attacks protection .
Information safety a lot edged activity field to him only systematic and complex
approach success to bring possible

Uzbekistan " Information " No. 439-II dated December 12, 2002 of the
Republic of freedom principles and guarantees "about". in the law information and
its types about the following definitions cited :

information - sources and presentation maturity from the form strictly look
persons , objects , facts , events , events and processes about information ;
information protection reach - information regarding to safety of threats prevention
get and their consequences eliminate reach measures ;

public information is unlimited in the circle intended for individuals
documented information , print , audio, audiovisual and another messages and
materials ;

documented information - identification to do enable giver requisites placed
without material in the body note done information ;

confidential information - use the law documents according to limiting to be
placed documented information . This definition Uzbekistan Republic Ministers "
Uzbekistan Republic President's " National information resources protection to do

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circle addition measures on » decision PQ-1572 of July 8, 2011 done increase measures in the decision No. 296 of November 7, 2011 as follows expressed as :

confidential information - Uzbekistan Republic the law documents according to use limited , state to secrets belongs to information there is didn't happen documented information .

Confidential information - documented information from him use the law documents according to is limited .

Storage , modification , transfer and known use for purposes a circle with an object universe about information , wide in a sense understand as information can To this concept according to man , his life a constant that affects his style and actions variable information area under the influence of will be Information own to the description according to political , military , economic , scientific and technical , production or to commerce about and secret , confidential or confidential to be can

Information safety concept , its founders description . Information safety when you say natural or artificial in character random or from intentional effects information and it supporting standing of infrastructure protection is understood . Such t a ' secrets ax b o r o t s o h a sid a gi information , including information to owners , from information to users and information protection to do supporting booster to the infrastructure serious damage deliver can

Uzbekistan No. 439-II of the Republic of December 12, 2002 " Information freedom principles and guarantees "about". in the law information safety information regarding It is defined as security and it is information in the field person , society and state interests protection situation means

Information in the field person interests of citizens from information to use circle constitutional rights done in the increase , in the law not prohibited activity with in his engagement and physical , spiritual and intellectual in development from information in their use , personal security provider information in defense manifestation will be

Information in the field society interests this in the field person interests in ensuring democracy in strengthening , social legal the state in construction , social solidarity in support own on the contrary finds

Information in the field state interests national information of infrastructure development conditions in creating information get in the field of individuals and citizens constitutional rights and freedoms done in the increase of Uzbekistan

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territorial unity , sovereignty and constitutionality of the system stability , political , economic and social stability provide in order to from information in use , legality and law order strictly done in the increase , mutually equality and reciprocity in interest international cooperation in development is expressed .

Information safety - a lot edged activity field to him only systematic , complex approach success to bring can This the problem solution in reaching legal , administrative , procedural and software- technical measures is used .

information security analysis .

Today's in the day information safety which provides three main principle there is :

- data integrity - information leading to loss from violations as well information authorship the right didn't happen generate without or no from doing protection to do
- of information confidentiality . Information and its of the carrier situation defines and in it information with unauthorized get to know or him unauthorized of documentation (copy) prevention of displacement get provided will be
- use has the rights (copyright) . all users from information use to get

Highlight OK , some activity sectors (banking and finance institutions , information networks , state management systems , defense and special structures) in them visible of issues to the importance and character according to their information systems activity reliability relatively high requirements and safety according to special measures needs to be seen .

Information of safety national safety in the system instead of in the 21st century person , society and state in development information resources and technologies role in Uzbekistan as a result of the increase citizenship society informed society as to build the issue solution reach with together the following factors national security provide in the system information of safety leader place take over defines :

- national interests , to them aggression and them this from attacks protect information and information is expressed through the field , done is increased .

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- man and his rights , information and information systems and to them ownership to do is not only information of safety main objects , perhaps safety in the field all safety of objects main elements is also
- information approach main scientific and practical method as national through use safety issues solution reach possible ;
- national safety problem obvious separate standing information to the description have

Information safety system of the state information in the field policy in the country national security provide state policy with closely connects In this information safety system state of politics the main founders whole one to the whole attaches . And this information of safety role and his country national safety in the system position determines Information in the field of Uzbekistan national interests , to them to reach strategic directions and them done increase systems in itself reflection bringer goals integrity state information policy means With that together state information policy of the country external and internal of politics main organizer is considered and of society all aspects cover takes

Information of safety modern concept information safety provider goals , tasks , principles and main directions according to official point of view glances set means

Below information of safety main constituents and aspects cited :

- information protection do (private data , state and service secrets and more kind of distribution limited information guarding in the sense of);
- computer safety or data security - computer in networks of information storage , use permission and confidentiality providing hardware and software tools collection , from information unauthorized from use protection to do measures ;
- information to the owners or from information to users and him supporting booster to the infrastructure damage deliver as natural as possible or artificial in character random or from intentional exposures information and it supporting booster of infrastructure protection ;
- citizens , individually groups and social layers , in general when of the population to live activity , education quality necessary for obtaining and development information requirements protection .

Information protection do - information security (data wholeness , use get and necessary when , enter data , save , re in performance and transmission usable

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information and its reserves confidentiality) is important aspects to provide directed events is a set .

Safe in the system from relevant hardware and software tools using information read , write , create and delete to the right have persons or they are on behalf of done which increases from information through processes use get managed .

As you know , absolutely safe systems there is not , but " to believe. " in the sense of possible system » reliable from systems is used . Enough hardware and software using , one of time in itself different confidentiality level information users group by use rights not broken without again work enable giver system reliable is considered

Reliability appraiser main criteria is safety policy and warranty .

Security policy - security objects and subjects given of abundance safety provide procedures and mechanisms determiner the rules collection . System safety of provision sure mechanisms choose perceived security to politics according to done is increased .

Guaranteed protect passive part from the system in use confidence in him level represents

Reliable in the system to safety concerned all processes registration need

Information protection to do concept information safety concept with closely depend

narrow sense information protection to do when you say information collection , transfer , re operation and storage in the process his security (confidentiality and integrity) . to provide directed events and activities set is understood . This is the definition information protection making and information safety concepts to each other near that means

Information security is that transmitted , collected and stored of information is a feature (state) of it external environment (human and nature) and internal from threats protection level characterizes .

Information protection to do wide in a sense information safety the threat prevention get and their complications no to do directed organizational , legal and technical measures complex means

Information protection to do sources of negative impact on information and causes and conditions detection and elimination reach the meaning means

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These are the sources information safety constitute threats . Information protection to do to the following addressed to :

- information safety provide according to of threats prevention get
- systematic real and probable through analysis and control grown up
- threats identify and them own in time prevention get measures ;
- sure threats and criminal actions to determine in order to threats to find
- criminal actions eliminate as well as sure criminal actions and threats no to do according to measures to see
- threatening and criminal of actions consequences no doing and position save

This all of methods purpose information resources illegal from threats protection to do and the following from providing consists of :

- confidential of information scatter to leave prevention get
- confidential information sources illegal access prohibition ;
- of information wholeness , completeness and from it use to receive storage ;
- information to confidentiality compliance to do
- authorship rights provide

Summary

The above taking into account the information protection to do when you say state , society and individuals information safety to provide directed methods , means and measures set to understand necessary

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